

Ubiquitous global use of persistent PFAS threatens Arctic Indigenous peoples for decades to come

Graphical abstract

Authors

Christian Sonne, Kim Gustavson, Rossana Bossi, Jens Søndergaard, Jean-Pierre Desforges, Eva Cecilie Bonfeld-Jørgensen, Rune Dietz

Correspondence

cs@ecos.au.dk

In brief

Sonne et al. examine East Greenlandic subsistence hunters' exposure to long-range-transported perfluoroalkyl chemicals (PFAS). Their analysis reveals that ~90% of the community exceeds the tolerable weekly intake by 13 times. The average person is expected to continue exceeding toxicity guidelines until 2090, posing risks of immune suppression and disease. The findings highlight the need for stricter PFAS regulation and non-toxic alternatives.

Highlights

- PFAS are found in polar bears and ringed seals in Greenland
- ~90% of the East Greenlandic hunting community exceeds TWI for immune effects by 13-fold
- Multi-generational toxication will continue until 2090
- Need for non-toxic compounds and global phase-out

Article

Ubiquitous global use of persistent PFAS threatens Arctic Indigenous peoples for decades to come

Christian Sonne,^{1,6,*} Kim Gustavson,¹ Rossana Bossi,² Jens Søndergaard,¹ Jean-Pierre Desforges,³ Eva Cecilie Bonefeld-Jørgensen,^{4,5} and Rune Dietz¹

¹Department of Ecoscience, Aarhus University, Arctic Research Centre, Frederiksborgvej 399, 4000 Roskilde, Denmark

²Department of Environmental Science, Aarhus University, Frederiksborgvej 399, 4000 Roskilde, Denmark

³Department of Environmental Studies and Science, University of Winnipeg, 515 Portage Avenue, Winnipeg, MB R3B 2E9, Canada

⁴Department of Public Health Centre for Arctic Health & Molecular Epidemiology, Aarhus University, Build. 1260, Bartholin Allé 2, 8000 Aarhus C, Denmark

⁵Greenland Centre for Health Research, University of Greenland, Nuussuaq, 3905 Nuuk, Greenland

⁶Lead contact

*Correspondence: cs@ecos.au.dk

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SCIENCE FOR SOCIETY Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are long-lasting pollutants that have been transported to the Arctic, where they pose health risks to wildlife and local subsistence hunters due to their immune-toxic properties. In this paper, we estimate the weekly exposure to these substances based on consumption of ringed seals and polar bears. We compare with established weekly tolerable intake levels, showing that the intake of the East Greenland Ittoqqortoormiit (Scoresby Sound) hunting community is far above this threshold for risk of immune suppression. Furthermore, based on temporal development in concentrations, the average inhabitant will continue to exceed toxicity guidelines until 2090, posing risks for disease susceptibility. Our study highlights the clear need for stricter PFAS regulation and non-toxic alternatives, particularly through international collaboration mechanisms, such as the Stockholm Convention, to ensure that vulnerable Indigenous communities are not affected by industrial pollutants.

SUMMARY

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are found in the environment worldwide due to their ubiquitous usage, global transport, and biological persistence. Here, we estimate the temporal dietary exposure to long-range-transported PFAS during 2006–2020 in the East Greenland Ittoqqortoormiit (Scoresby Sound) community based on consumption of traditional marine foods as compared with internationally established tolerable weekly intake (TWI) for immune toxicity of 4.4 ng/kg body weight. We found a biomagnification factor of 4–10 between ringed seal:polar bear and estimate that ~90% of the Ittoqqortoormiit community exceeded the established \sum_4 PFAS TWI by 13-fold through consumption of polar bears and ringed seals. We estimate that the average inhabitant will continue to exceed established toxicity guidelines until 2090, posing the risk of immune suppression and disease susceptibility. Our findings emphasize the need for additional regulation of PFAS and the development of non-toxic sustainable compounds through international collaboration, not least through the Stockholm Convention.

INTRODUCTION

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are resistant to environmental and biological degradation and excretion and are therefore found ubiquitously in the environment as well as in humans and wildlife.^{1–3} These industrial “forever chemicals” are broadly used in commercial and consumer products, including non-stick and stain-resistant cookware, food packaging such as pizza boxes, and waterproof rain wear.⁴ In addition, PFAS are used as constituents in foams to extinguish fuel-based fires

used for training exercises, aircraft crashes, and other fuel fires.⁵ The broad and high-tonnage global usage of PFAS results in contamination of drinking water and the environment, which poses major threats to humans and biodiversity.^{6–12}

The persistent and proteophilic characteristics of PFAS allow them to biomagnify in marine food webs leading, to high concentrations in liver, kidney, muscle, and blood in high-trophic feeders like marine mammals and Indigenous peoples.^{13,14} In environmental samples, perfluorooctane sulfonate (PFOS) is the dominant PFAS. The European Food Safety Authority

Figure 1. Circumpolar mapping and trophic transfer

(A) Shows the study location of Ittoqqortoormiit community (yellow circle) and the dominating ocean and atmospheric transport routes.

(B) Shows conceptual trophic transfer of the dominant PFAS, perfluorooctane sulfonate (PFOS), in the Eastern Arctic marine food webs.

(EFSA) has determined that PFOS is immunotoxic due, in part, to its ability to reduce antigen-specific antibody production (i.e., immunization efficacy).^{15–17} Moreover, studies suggest that other PFAS may also reduce immunization efficacy, including that in children, which suggests that exposure to PFAS may be a risk factor for pandemics and other infectious diseases.^{15,18–20} PFAS exposure has also been linked to effects on other physiological processes, increasing the risk of thyroid disease, elevated cholesterol levels, liver disease, kidney and testicular cancer, and developmental effects such as decreased birth weight.^{2,21} These major immunotoxic effects and other health risks highlight the need to monitor hot-spot communities and assess environmental burdens to assess the risk of exposure to humans and wildlife.^{8,10,22–24}

The exposure of humans, including Arctic peoples, to PFAS occurs worldwide^{8,25} (Figure 1). PFAS are transported over large distances to the Arctic, from sources in industrialized regions at more southern latitudes, through atmospheric deposition and marine and riverine inputs.²⁵ Some PFAS have been found in apex predators such as polar bears (*Ursus maritimus*) in concentrations up to at least 1,000,000 times higher than in phytoplankton at the base of the food web (Figure 1).^{8,10} This food web magnification not only threatens polar bears but, importantly, also puts local Inuit communities at even higher risk due to their traditional diet of country foods that includes polar bears, seals, toothed whales, and other marine species.^{10,26} A recent review of regional concentration and profile differences across the circumpolar Arctic during the 2010–2020 period show the highest PFAS levels in Greenlandic men increasing with age.²⁷ In addition, concentrations of regulated PFAS under the Stockholm Convention, including PFOS, perfluoro-octanoate (PFOA), and perfluorohexane sulfonate (PFHxS), decreased during the study period, whereas unregulated PFAS, including perfluorononanoic acid (PFNA), perfluorodecanoic acid (PFDA), and perfluoroundecanoic acid (PFUnDA), increased.

Here, we combine time-trend data (2006–2020) as well as future projections of PFAS tissue levels in polar bears and ringed seals (*Pusa hispida*) with food intake data from Inuit in Ittoqqortoormiit (Scoresby Sound), Central East Greenland, to charac-

terize exposure and risk of adverse health effects to this population. We aim to (1) determine the biomagnification of PFAS along the human food chain, including ringed seals and polar bears, (2) estimate the individual and community exposure to PFAS and their associated risks for adverse immune response, and (3) forecast future PFAS exposure in the East Greenlandic Inuit over the next century to estimate when prolonged risks for adverse immune effects fall below established toxicity guidelines.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Trophic transfer along the human food chain

The concentration of Σ_4 PFAS (i.e., sum of PFOS, PFOA, PFHxS, and PFNA) was highest in polar bear liver (mean: 1,665; range:160–4,869 ng/g ww), followed by ringed seal liver (108; 22.9–483 ng/g ww), polar bear muscle (19.4; 6.69–74.4 ng/g ww), and ringed seal muscle (5.8; 1.77–16.6 ng/g ww) (Figure 2). The higher concentrations of PFAS in liver tissues than muscle was expected, as these show different phospholipid levels and metabolic differences.^{8,11,28,29} Concentrations in polar bears are above levels reported in other marine mammal populations around the world, reflecting significant long-range transport from southern latitudes into the Arctic and the long and slow-growing Arctic food webs.^{25,30} The Inuit exposure is lower than it is for polar bears due to the local diet mix of marine mammals and store food³¹ (Figure 1).

Based on the mean tissue values, the Σ_4 PFAS bio-magnification factor of polar bear:ringed seal is 3.8 and 9.7 for muscle and liver, respectively, similar to previous findings in respect of Arctic food webs^{8,11,13,32} and elsewhere in global marine ecosystems.^{33–36} Overall, these findings show that PFAS transfers across the food chain and accumulates at elevated levels in top predators. The higher trophic position of polar bears puts them at greater health risk than ringed seals. Indeed, the use of physiologically based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) modeling has shown that the concentrations of PFOS in East Greenlandic polar bears increases the risk of, especially, cancer, immune suppression, and diminished reproductive success.^{22,23,37,38} This highlights the risk from long-range pollution on the Arctic's top marine predators as well as on Arctic biodiversity, as previously outlined.^{10,22,23}

Human exposure and risks

Weekly consumption of ringed seal muscle and liver varies in the community to a greater extent than consumption of polar bear

Figure 2. PFAS in East Greenlandic polar bears and ringed seals 2006–2020

(A) Shows boxplot (median, 25% and 75% quantiles) of Σ_4 PFAS in liver and muscle tissue. (B) Shows correlation of Σ_4 PFAS in liver and muscle tissue for polar bears. (C) Shows correlations of Σ_4 PFAS in liver and muscle tissue for ringed seals. 95% confidence bands are shown for (B) and (C).

muscle (Table S1). Based on the EFSA tolerable weekly intake (TWI) threshold value of 4.4 ng/kg body weight/week for long-term Σ_4 PFAS exposure, and the median concentration of Σ_4 PFAS of 13.3 ng/g ww (25th–75th percentile: 10.6–18.8 ng/g ww) in polar bear muscle, we estimate that current weekly consumption of polar bear muscle by children (30 kg), women (60 kg), and men (70 kg) should not exceed 9.9 (7.0–12.4), 19.8 (14–24.8), and 23.1 (16.4–29.0) g, respectively (Figure 3). Similarly, current weekly consumption of ringed seal liver by children, women, and men should not exceed 3.4 (2.1–3.8), 6.8 (4.3–7.5), and 8.0 (5.0–8.8) g, respectively, and current consumption of ringed seal muscle by children, women, and men should not exceed 23.6 (18.2–33.7), 47.2 (36.5–67.3), and 55.1 (42.5–78.6) g, respectively (Figure 3). Actual consumption shows current median weekly intake of the three tissues being 280 g in total (Table S1), highlighting an unsustainable long-term diet of polar bears and ringed seals for the Inuit society.

Using Monte Carlo-simulated data on weekly liver and muscle consumption and associated Σ_4 PFAS concentrations, we estimate the percentage of the population above the EFSA TWI to be 84%, 80%, and 69% for consumption of polar bear muscle, ringed seal liver, and ringed seal muscle, respectively (Figure 4A). Considering combined consumption of all three tissues from the two species, we estimate that 89% of the population exceeds the EFSA TWI threshold for immunological health effects (Figure 4B). The high percentage of the population exceeding available toxicity guidelines reflects the long-range-transport potential of PFAS, combined with its persistence and high levels in marine species, in the Arctic.^{8,25,39–41} Inuit in Ittoqqortoormiit have previously been found to have among the highest blood serum levels of PFAS in the circumpolar Arctic.^{8,31,42} In fact, polar bear consumers in East Greenland have the highest-reported non-occupationally exposed serum concentrations worldwide despite the region's remoteness.^{8,42} This clearly highlights that there is a need to protect remote communities from high PFAS exposure through country food, including, in particular, pregnant and breastfeeding women, in whom the transfer of chemicals can occur

across the placenta and through milk to vulnerable unborn and newborn children.^{43–45}

Temporal trends and predicted future PFAS intake

Our temporal trend analysis revealed that the annual percentage change for Σ_4 PFAS is non-linear in polar bear liver, although statistically significant linear declines were found for polar bear muscle (–4.2% per year) and ringed seal liver (–11.7% per year) (Figure 5). Σ_4 PFAS in ringed seal muscle showed a non-significant decline (–1.1% per year). The declining trend in polar bear muscle and ringed seal liver and muscle is relevant to Inuit, as these tissues are routinely consumed, whereas the increasing trend in recent years for polar bear liver is less concerning for the community as they do not consume this tissue because of the need to avoid hypervitaminosis A.⁴⁶

Time trends for each PFAS varied, depending on tissue and species (Figures S1–S4). In ringed seals, PFNA and PFHxS increase in both liver and muscle, whereas all PFAS increase in polar bear liver but only PFNA in polar bear muscle. The increasing trend of Σ_4 PFAS in polar bear liver since 2015 indicates a change in diet or dietary sources of the East Greenlandic polar bear subpopulation that is not reflected in muscle due to Σ_4 PFAS toxicokinetic and the metabolic characteristics of liver tissue.²⁹ Previous studies have shown that climate change and loss of sea-ice has made the East Greenlandic polar bear population shift their diet toward high-trophic seal species, and they increasingly consuming hooded seals (*Cystophora cristata*) at the expense of ringed seals.^{47,48} It is therefore likely that the increases in Σ_4 PFAS in polar bear liver are due to changes in hooded seal access along its breeding and molting patches due to sea-ice reduction as well as well as increased use of PFNA and PFHxS due to the regulation and decreasing use of PFOS.³¹

As an exercise to explore when Inuit from Ittoqqortoormiit may stop exceeding the EFSA TWI values for immunological effects from Σ_4 PFAS dietary intake, we use existing consumption estimates (current study) and Σ_4 PFAS time trends in polar bear and ringed seal tissues (% annual decline, Figure 5) to extrapolate future Σ_4 PFAS weekly intake. Specifically, we estimate

Figure 3. Tolerable weekly intake (TWI) for PFAS in the Ittoqqortoormiit community, East Greenland 2018–2020, for children (30), women (60), and men (70)

(A) Shows EFSA TWI for individual polar bear muscle concentrations of Σ_4 PFAS.

(B) Shows EFSA TWI for individual ringed seal liver concentrations of Σ_4 PFAS.

(C) Shows EFSA TWI for individual ringed seal muscle concentrations of Σ_4 PFAS.

Solid and stipulated lines show median and quantile (25% and 75%, respectively).

intake of Σ_4 PFAS for polar bear muscle, ringed seal liver, and ringed seal muscle (g/week), based on predicted median (25th–75th quantiles) concentrations in those respective tissues each year for the period 2020–2125, and compare the combined Σ_4 PFAS intake from all tissues to the EFSA TWI (Figure 6). Our approach shows that Σ_4 PFAS intake for a 60-kg Ittoqqortoormiit Inuit is 13-fold higher (25th–75th percentile: 11–20) than the EFSA TWI value and that the fold-increase above the TWI declines over time (Figure 6). Only by 2090 does the median weekly

Σ_4 PFAS intake fall below the EFSA TWI value. This approach does not account for unknown future changes in Inuit marine mammal consumption patterns or Σ_4 PFAS profile. The prolonged elevated risk persists for at least three generations from now and could have significant implications for the health of the community, where PFAS may increase the risks of multi-generational epigenetic changes and disease prevalence.^{49–51} It has been shown that PFAS exposure is of concern to highly exposed populations as it reduces the efficacy of vaccines.^{15,18,19,52,53} However, as outlined above, in addition to immune health, PFAS exposure is also related to several other disease complexes, including thyroid, androgen, and estrogen hormone disruption and effects on fetal growth, breast cancer, infections, and cardiometabolic and respiratory disease.^{38,54–63} The mechanisms behind these health effects are diverse and complex, involving a broad range of physiological processes.^{16,20,24,64,65}

Considerations

The present study shows that 89% of the Ittoqqortoormiit (Scoresby Sound) population exceeds the TWI of 4.4 ng/kg body weight in non-pregnant adults for Σ_4 PFAS, which raises significant concerns for immunotoxic effects. When combining tissue consumption, a maximum of 5–10 g of tissues can currently be eaten weekly to stay below the EFSA TWI, which seems unrealistic according to the findings of the food frequency questionnaire (FFQ). Here, it should be noted that marine mammal meat consumption is seasonal and there will be times of the year when intake will fall above and below these estimated toxicity levels. Furthermore, temporal projections show that consumption by the average community member does not fall below the EFSA TWI before the end of this century, highlighting the severity of long-range transport of industrial chemicals into the Arctic. This assessment focuses strictly on PFAS, but we know that many heavy metals and persistent organic pollutants (POPs) also accumulate in marine food webs and pose additional risks to wildlife and Indigenous peoples in the Arctic, not least given that these substances travel across the placenta and into milk.^{43–45,66} To protect these highly exposed Arctic populations,

results like the present are used by the Greenland Self-Government to inform its physician’s development consumption guidelines in tandem with consideration of healthy alternatives and low-cost food to help resolve the Arctic dilemma. The findings of this research and the growing knowledge of PFAS pollution globally highlight the urgent need to better regulate PFAS and other persistent, bioaccumulative, and toxic chemicals through national and international efforts such as the Stockholm Convention. These regulations need to be combined with sustainable initiatives in the field of chemistry to alleviate socio-economic costs through investments in green chemistry and non-toxic solutions.

Conclusions

We found a biomagnification factor of 4–10 between ringed seal:polar bear and estimated that ~90% of the Ittoqqortoormiit community exceeded the established Σ_4 PFAS TWI by 13-fold through consumption of polar bears and ringed seals and that the average inhabitant will continue to exceed established

Figure 4. Weekly tissue consumption and associated PFAS intake in the Ittoqqortoormiit community, East Greenland 2018–2020

(A) Shows empirical and Monte Carlo-simulated weekly consumption (g) of polar bear muscle, ringed seal liver, ringed seal muscle, and combination of all three. (B) Shows Monte Carlo simulation of Σ_4 PFAS weekly intake (ng/kg body weight) compared with EFSA TWI of 4.4 ng/kg body weight (solid vertical line). Standard boxplots shown underneath (median, 25%, 75% quantiles).

toxicity guidelines until 2090 if the current trends continue. The prolonged elevated exposure to PFAS in this Inuit community over the next century is concerning in terms of multi-generational disease prevalence and non-infectious diseases such as cardio-metabolic diseases, cancer, and reduced fertility. Our findings emphasize the need for additional regulation of PFAS and the development of non-toxic sustainable compounds through international collaboration, not least through the Stockholm Convention.

METHODS

Muscle and liver tissue were sampled from polar bears ($n = 95$) and ringed seals ($n = 52$) of different age and sex, collected in the period 2006–2020 as part of the Ittoqqortoormiit community subsistence harvest in East Greenland (further details regarding the methods can be found in [Tables S1](#) and [S2](#)). All polar bear tissue samples were legally exported using The International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES) export and import permissions from Greenland to Denmark, as outlined in [supplemental information](#), and kept frozen until arrival at the Department of Ecoscience, Aarhus University (Roskilde). The concentration of Σ_4 PFAS (PFOS, PFOA, PFHxS, and PFNA) was analyzed at the Department of Environmental Science, Aarhus University, Roskilde, Denmark (see [supplemental information](#)). Sixteen anonymous inhabitants of Ittoqqortoormiit (8 subsistence hunters and 8 non-subsistence hunters), representing $\sim 5\%$ of the total community population, filled out a life-

style and FFQ designed for Inuit ($n = 16$) (further details regarding the methods can be found in the [supplemental information](#)).^{8,67,68} The FFQ was approved by the Ethical Committee for Scientific Investigations in Greenland (KVUG) and Nunatsinni Nakorsaaneqarfik and was conducted in accordance with the Helsinki Declaration. The FFQ was used in this study to estimate the weekly consumption (g/week) of ringed seal muscle and liver as well as polar bear muscle (g/week) of the participants (further details regarding the methods can be found in [Table S1](#)). We focus on polar bear and ringed seal, as a previous study found these to be the most important dietary sources for PFAS exposure in Ittoqqortoormiit.⁶ Weekly tissue intake was combined with tissue-specific Σ_4 PFAS concentrations (further details regarding the methods can be found in [Tables S1–S3](#)) to estimate long-term weekly dietary exposure to Σ_4 PFAS. These Σ_4 PFAS consumption estimates were then compared with the EFSA 2020 TWI of 4.4 ng/kg body weight for immune toxicity in non-pregnant adults (further details regarding the methods can be found in the [supplemental information](#)).^{69,70} All statistical analyses and graphics were performed in R version 4.2.3. The relationship between muscle and liver concentrations was investigated using linear regression analysis. Time trends for PFOS, PFOA, PFNA, PFHxS, and Σ_4 PFAS in polar bear and ringed seals from 2006 to 2020 were explored using the Harmonized Regional Seas Assessment Tool (HARSAT) package version 1.0.0 (<https://harsat.amap.no>). Briefly, a model with a log linear trend is fitted to the data to assess change in patterns and then compared with a non-linear trend model in which concentrations varied smoothly (and non linearly) over time. Then, depending on the

Figure 5. Temporal trends of PFAS during 2006–2020

(A) Shows Σ_4 PFAS in polar bear liver.
(B) Shows Σ_4 PFAS in polar bear muscle.
(C) Shows Σ_4 PFAS in ringed seal liver.
(D) Shows Σ_4 PFAS in ringed seal muscle.
Data are shown as annual medians with 95% confidence band.
The individual compound trends are shown in Figures S1–S4.

length of the time series, smoothers are fitted on up to 4 degrees of freedom, after which the model with the lowest Akaike information criterion, corrected for small sample size, is selected.⁷¹ We use Monte Carlo simulations on weekly tissue consumption and weekly Σ_4 PFAS intake to expand on our small sample sizes to explore general patterns in the risk of adverse immunological effects for the Ittoqqortoormiit community. Specifically, we

simulate 2,500 data points from a normal distribution assuming mean and standard deviations from empirical data of tissue consumption (g/week) and Σ_4 PFAS intake. No truncation was applied, as improbable values (i.e., <0) represented less than 1% of the simulated data.

RESOURCE AVAILABILITY

Lead contact

Further information and results for resources and reagents should be directed to and will be fulfilled by the lead contact, Christian Sonne (cs@ecos.au.dk).

Materials availability

This study did not generate new unique materials.

Data and code availability

All data reported in this article will be shared by the lead contact upon request. This paper does not report any original code(s). Any additional information required to reanalyze the data reported in this paper is available from the lead contact upon request. In addition, all data are available in the main text or in the supplemental information.

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Figure 6. Predicted temporal decrease in Σ_4 PFAS exposure during 2020–2125 relative to the TWI

Shows fold above TWI for a 60-kg Ittoqqortoormiit Inuit. Solid and stipulated blue lines are median and quantile (25%, 75%). Orange lines show the years when each (median, 25% and 75% quantile) simulation falls below 1. The estimate is based on Tables S1–S4.

using IUCN CITES export and import permissions from Greenland to Denmark.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Conceptualization: C.S., E.C.B.-J., and R.D. Methodology: C.S., J.-P.D., J.S., K.G., R.B., E.C.B.-J., and R.D. Investigation: C.S., J.-P.D., E.C.B.-J., and R.D. Visualization: C.S., J.-P.D., K.G., J.S., and R.D. Funding acquisition: C.S., R.B., E.C.B.-J., and R.D. Project administration: C.S. Supervision: C.S., J.-P.D., J.S., K.G., and R.D. Writing – original draft: C.S., J.-P.D., and K.G. Writing – review & editing: C.S., J.-P.D., J.S., K.G., R.B., E.C.B.-J., and R.D.

DECLARATION OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no competing interests.

SUPPLEMENTAL INFORMATION

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REFERENCES

- Chohan, A., Petaway, H., Rivera-Diaz, V., Day, A., Colaianni, O., and Keramati, M. (2021). Per and polyfluoroalkyl substances scientific literature review: water exposure, impact on human health, and implications for regulatory reform. *Rev. Environ. Health* 36, 235–259. <https://doi.org/10.1515/revh-2020-0049>.
- Sunderland, E.M., Hu, X.C., Dassuncao, C., Tokranov, A.K., Wagner, C.C., and Allen, J.G. (2019). A review of the pathways of human exposure to poly- and perfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) and present understanding of health effects. *J. Expo. Sci. Environ. Epidemiol.* 29, 131–147. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41370-018-0094-1>.
- Evich, M.G., Davis, M.J.B., McCord, J.P., Acrey, B., Awkerman, J.A., Knappe, D.R.U., Lindstrom, A.B., Speth, T.F., Tebes-Stevens, C., Strynar, M.J., et al. (2022). Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances in the environment. *Science* 375, eabg9065. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abg9065>.
- Braun, J.M. (2023). Enhancing Regulations to Reduce Exposure to PFAS – Federal Action on “Forever Chemicals”. *N. Engl. J. Med.* 388, 1924–1926. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMp2303333>.
- Scheringer, M. (2023). Innovate beyond PFAS. *Science* 381, 251. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adj7475>.
- De Silva, A.O., Armitage, J.M., Bruton, T.A., Dassuncao, C., Heiger-Bernays, W., Hu, X.C., Kärrman, A., Kelly, B., Ng, C., Robuck, A., et al. (2021). PFAS Exposure Pathways for Humans and Wildlife: A Synthesis of Current Knowledge and Key Gaps in Understanding. *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* 40, 631–657. <https://doi.org/10.1002/etc.4935>.
- Whitehead, H.D., Venier, M., Wu, Y., Eastman, E., Urbanik, S., Diamond, M.L., Shalin, A., Schwartz-Narbonne, H., Bruton, T.A., Blum, A., et al. (2021). Fluorinated Compounds in North American Cosmetics. *Environ. Sci. Technol. Lett.* 8, 538–544. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.estlett.1c00240>.
- Sonne, C., Desforges, J.P., Gustavson, K., Bossi, R., Bonefeld-Jørgensen, E.C., Long, M., Rigét, F.F., and Dietz, R. (2023). Assessment of exposure to perfluorinated industrial substances and risk of immune suppression in Greenland and its global context: a mixed-methods study. *Lancet Planet Health* 7, e570–e579. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2542-5196\(23\)00106-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2542-5196(23)00106-7).
- Sonne, C., Vorkamp, K., Galatius, A., Kyhn, L., Teilmann, J., Bossi, R., Søndergaard, J., Eulaers, I., Desforges, J.P., Siebert, U., et al. (2019). Human exposure to PFOS and mercury through meat from baltic harbour seals (*Phoca vitulina*). *Environ. Res.* 175, 376–383. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2019.05.026>.
- Dietz, R., Letcher, R.J., Desforges, J.-P., Eulaers, I., Sonne, C., Wilson, S., Andersen-Ranberg, E., Basu, N., Barst, B.D., Bustnes, J.O., et al. (2019). Current state of knowledge on biological effects from contaminants on arctic wildlife and fish. *Sci. Total Environ.* 696, 133792. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.133792>.
- Boisvert, G., Sonne, C., Rigét, F.F., Dietz, R., and Letcher, R.J. (2019). Bioaccumulation and biomagnification of perfluoroalkyl acids and precursors in East Greenland polar bears and their ringed seal prey. *Environ. Pollut.* 252, 1335–1343. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2019.06.035>.
- Rigét, F., Bignert, A., Braune, B., Dam, M., Dietz, R., Evans, M., Green, N., Gunnlaugsdóttir, H., Hoydal, K.S., Kucklick, J., et al. (2019). Temporal trends of persistent organic pollutants in Arctic marine and freshwater biota. *Sci. Total Environ.* 649, 99–110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.08.268>.
- Bossi, R., Rigét, F.F., Dietz, R., Sonne, C., Fauser, P., Dam, M., and Vorkamp, K. (2005). Preliminary screening of perfluorooctane sulfonate (PFOS) and other fluorochemicals in fish, birds and marine mammals from Greenland and the Faroe Islands. *Environ. Pollut.* 136, 323–329. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2004.12.020>.
- Sonne, C., Dietz, R., Jenssen, B.M., Lam, S.S., and Letcher, R.J. (2021). Emerging contaminants and biological effects in Arctic wildlife. *Trends Ecol. Evol.* 36, 421–429. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2021.01.007>.
- Grandjean, P., Andersen, E.W., Budtz-Jørgensen, E., Nielsen, F., Mølbak, K., Weihe, P., and Heilmann, C. (2012). Serum vaccine antibody concentrations in children exposed to perfluorinated compounds. *JAMA* 307, 391–397. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2011.2034>.
- Beans, C. (2021). News Feature: How “forever chemicals” might impair the immune system. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 118, e2105018118. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2105018118>.
- Corsini, E., Iulini, M., Galbiati, V., Maddalon, A., Pappalardo, F., Russo, G., Hoogenboom, R.L.A.P., Beekmann, K., Janssen, A.W.F., Louisse, J., et al. (2024). EFSA Project on the use of NAMs to explore the immunotoxicity of PFAS. *EFSA Support. Publ.* 21, 8926E. <https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2024.EN-8926>.
- Timmermann, C.A.G., Pedersen, H.S., Weihe, P., Bjerregaard, P., Nielsen, F., Heilmann, C., and Grandjean, P. (2022). Concentrations of tetanus and diphtheria antibodies in vaccinated Greenlandic children aged 7–12 years exposed to marine pollutants, a cross sectional study. *Environ. Res.* 203, 111712. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2021.111712>.
- Shih, Y.H., Blomberg, A.J., Bind, M.A., Holm, D., Nielsen, F., Heilmann, C., Weihe, P., and Grandjean, P. (2021). Serum vaccine antibody concentrations in adults exposed to per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances: A birth cohort in the Faroe Islands. *J. Immunotoxicol.* 18, 85–92. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1547691x.2021.1922957>.
- Grandjean, P., Timmermann, C.A.G., Kruse, M., Nielsen, F., Vinholt, P.J., Boding, L., Heilmann, C., and Mølbak, K. (2020). Severity of COVID-19 at elevated exposure to perfluorinated alkylates. *PLoS One* 15, e0244815. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0244815>.

21. Fenton, S.E., Ducatman, A., Boobis, A., DeWitt, J.C., Lau, C., Ng, C., Smith, J.S., and Roberts, S.M. (2021). Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substance Toxicity and Human Health Review: Current State of Knowledge and Strategies for Informing Future Research. *Environ. Toxicol. Chem.* **40**, 606–630. <https://doi.org/10.1002/etc.4890>.
22. Dietz, R., Desforages, J.P., Gustavson, K., Rigét, F.F., Born, E.W., Letcher, R.J., and Sonne, C. (2018). Immunologic, reproductive, and carcinogenic risk assessment from POP exposure in East Greenland polar bears (*Ursus maritimus*) during 1983–2013. *Environ. Int.* **118**, 169–178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2018.05.020>.
23. Dietz, R., Gustavson, K., Sonne, C., Desforages, J.P., Rigét, F.F., Pavlova, V., McKinney, M.A., and Letcher, R.J. (2015). Physiologically-based pharmacokinetic modelling of immune, reproductive and carcinogenic effects from contaminant exposure in polar bears (*Ursus maritimus*) across the Arctic. *Environ. Res.* **140**, 45–55. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2015.03.011>.
24. Desforages, J.P.W., Sonne, C., Levin, M., Siebert, U., De Guise, S., and Dietz, R. (2016). Immunotoxic effects of environmental pollutants in marine mammals. *Environ. Int.* **86**, 126–139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2015.10.007>.
25. Muir, D., Bossi, R., Carlsson, P., Evans, M., De Silva, A., Halsall, C., Rauert, C., Herzke, D., Hung, H., Letcher, R., et al. (2019). Levels and trends of poly- and perfluoroalkyl substances in the Arctic environment – An update. *Emerging Contam.* **5**, 240–271. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emcon.2019.06.002>.
26. Caron-Beaudoin, É., Ayotte, P., Blanchette, C., Muckle, G., Avard, E., Ricard, S., and Lemire, M. (2020). Perfluoroalkyl acids in pregnant women from Nunavik (Quebec, Canada): Trends in exposure and associations with country foods consumption. *Environ. Int.* **145**, 106169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.106169>.
27. Bonefeld-Jørgensen, E.C. (2023). Perfluoroalkyl Substances in the Circumpolar Arctic and Northern Populations. *ACT* **8**, 1–13.
28. Dassuncao, C., Pickard, H., Pfohl, M., Tokranov, A.K., Li, M., Mikkelsen, B., Slitt, A., and Sunderland, E.M. (2019). Phospholipid Levels Predict the Tissue Distribution of Poly- and Perfluoroalkyl Substances in a Marine Mammal. *Environ. Sci. Technol. Lett.* **6**, 119–125. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.estlett.9b00031>.
29. Wang, P., Liu, D., Yan, S., Cui, J., Liang, Y., and Ren, S. (2022). Adverse Effects of Perfluorooctane Sulfonate on the Liver and Relevant Mechanisms. *Toxics* **10**, 265. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxics10050265>.
30. Fair, P.A., and Houde, M. (2018). Poly- and Perfluoroalkyl Substances in Marine Mammals Chapter 5. In *Marine Mammal Ecotoxicology*, M.C. Fossi and C. Panti, eds. (Academic Press), pp. 117–145. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-812144-3.00005-X>.
31. Lohmann, R., Abass, K., Bonefeld-Jørgensen, E.C., Bossi, R., Dietz, R., Ferguson, S., Fernie, K.J., Grandjean, P., Herzke, D., Houde, M., et al. (2024). Cross-cutting studies of per- and polyfluorinated alkyl substances (PFAS) in Arctic wildlife and humans. *Sci. Total Environ.* **954**, 176274. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.176274>.
32. Tomy, G.T., Budakowski, W., Halldorsen, T., Helm, P.A., Stern, G.A., Friesen, K., Pepper, K., Tittlemier, S.A., and Fisk, A.T. (2004). Fluorinated organic compounds in an eastern Arctic marine food web. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **38**, 6475–6481. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es049620g>.
33. Houde, M., Bujas, T.A.D., Small, J., Wells, R.S., Fair, P.A., Bossart, G.D., Solomon, K.R., and Muir, D.C.G. (2006). Biomagnification of perfluoroalkyl compounds in the bottlenose dolphin (*Tursiops truncatus*) food web. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **40**, 4138–4144. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es060233b>.
34. Cara, B., Lies, T., Thimo, G., Robin, L., and Lieven, B. (2022). Bioaccumulation and trophic transfer of perfluorinated alkyl substances (PFAS) in marine biota from the Belgian North Sea: Distribution and human health risk implications. *Environ. Pollut.* **311**, 119907. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2022.119907>.
35. Stockin, K.A., Yi, S., Northcott, G.L., Betty, E.L., Machovsky-Capuska, G.E., Jones, B., Perrott, M.R., Law, R.J., Rumsby, A., Thelen, M.A., et al. (2021). Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), trace elements and life history parameters of mass-stranded common dolphins (*Delphinus delphis*) in New Zealand. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* **173**, 112896. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2021.112896>.
36. Van de Vijver, K.I., Hoff, P.T., Das, K., Van Dongen, W., Esmans, E.L., Jau-niaux, T., Bouquegneau, J.M., Blust, R., and de Coen, W. (2003). Perfluorinated chemicals infiltrate ocean waters: link between exposure levels and stable isotope ratios in marine mammals. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **37**, 5545–5550. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es0345975>.
37. Sonne, C., Gustavson, K., Rigét, F.F., Dietz, R., Birkved, M., Letcher, R.J., Bossi, R., Vorkamp, K., Born, E.W., and Petersen, G. (2009). Reproductive performance in East Greenland polar bears (*Ursus maritimus*) may be affected by organohalogen contaminants as shown by physiologically-based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) modelling. *Chemosphere* **77**, 1558–1568. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2009.09.044>.
38. Bonefeld-Jørgensen, E.C., Long, M., Bossi, R., Ayotte, P., Asmund, G., Krüger, T., Ghisari, M., Mulvad, G., Kern, P., Nzulumiki, P., et al. (2011). Perfluorinated compounds are related to breast cancer risk in Greenlandic Inuit: a case control study. *Environ. Health* **10**, 88. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1476-069x-10-88>.
39. Turgeon O'Brien, H., Gagné, D., Lauzière, J., Blanchet, R., Vézina, C., and Ayotte, P. (2019). Temporal trends of legacy and emerging persistent organic pollutants in Inuit preschoolers from Northern Quebec (Canada). *Int. J. Environ. Health Res.* **29**, 643–656. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09603123.2018.1560396>.
40. Wielsøe, M., Kern, P., and Bonefeld-Jørgensen, E.C. (2017). Serum levels of environmental pollutants is a risk factor for breast cancer in Inuit: a case control study. *Environ. Health* **16**, 56. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12940-017-0269-6>.
41. Ghisari, M., Eiberg, H., Long, M., and Bonefeld-Jørgensen, E.C. (2014). Polymorphisms in phase I and phase II genes and breast cancer risk and relations to persistent organic pollutant exposure: a case-control study in Inuit women. *Environ. Health* **13**, 19. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1476-069x-13-19>.
42. Long, M., Sonne, C., Dietz, R., Bossi, R., Jørgensen, N., Olsen, T.I., and Bonefeld-Jørgensen, E.C. (2023). Diet, lifestyle and contaminants in three east Greenland Inuit municipalities. *Chemosphere* **344**, 140368. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2023.140368>.
43. Appel, M., Forsthuber, M., Ramos, R., Widhalm, R., Granitzer, S., Uhl, M., Hengstschläger, M., Stamm, T., and Gundacker, C. (2022). The transplacental transfer efficiency of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS): a first meta-analysis. *J. Toxicol. Environ. Health B Crit. Rev.* **25**, 23–42. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10937404.2021.2009946>.
44. Forn, J., Verner, M.A., Iszatt, N., Nowack, N., Bach, C.C., Vrijheid, M., Costa, O., Andriana, A., Sovcikova, E., Høyer, B.B., et al. (2020). Early Life Exposure to Perfluoroalkyl Substances (PFAS) and ADHD: A Meta-Analysis of Nine European Population-Based Studies. *Environ. Health Perspect.* **128**, 57002. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp5444>.
45. Ayotte, P., Muckle, G., Jacobson, J.L., Jacobson, S.W., and Dewailly, E.; Inuit Cohort Study (2003). Assessment of pre- and postnatal exposure to polychlorinated biphenyls: lessons from the Inuit Cohort Study. *Environ. Health Perspect.* **111**, 1253–1258. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.6054>.
46. Rodahl, K., and Moore, T. (1943). The vitamin A content and toxicity of bear and seal liver. *Biochem. J.* **37**, 166–168. <https://doi.org/10.1042/bj0370166>.
47. McKinney, M.A., Iverson, S.J., Fisk, A.T., Sonne, C., Rigét, F.F., Letcher, R.J., Arts, M.T., Born, E.W., Rosing-Asvid, A., and Dietz, R. (2013). Global change effects on the long-term feeding ecology and contaminant exposures of East Greenland polar bears. *Glob. Chang. Biol.* **19**, 2360–2372. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12241>.
48. Dietz, R., Rigét, F.F., Eulaers, I., Desforages, J.-P., Vorkamp, K., Bossi, R., Søndergaard, J., Ambus, P.M., Letcher, R.L., et al. (2021). Unexpected Increases of Persistent Organic Pollutant and Mercury levels in East

- Greenland Polar Bears (UNEXPECTED) (Aarhus University, DCE – Danish Centre for Environment and Energy). <http://dce2.au.dk/pub/TR214.pdf>.
49. Kim, S., Thapar, I., and Brooks, B.W. (2021). Epigenetic changes by per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS). *Environ. Pollut.* 279, 116929. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2021.116929>.
 50. Boyd, R.I., Ahmad, S., Singh, R., Fazal, Z., Prins, G.S., Madak Erdogan, Z., Irudayaraj, J., and Spinella, M.J. (2022). Toward a Mechanistic Understanding of Poly- and Perfluoroalkylated Substances and Cancer. *Cancers (Basel)* 14, 2919. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers14122919>.
 51. Maxwell, D.L., Oluwayiose, O.A., Houle, E., Roth, K., Nowak, K., Sawant, S., Paskavitz, A.L., Liu, W., Gurdziel, K., Petriello, M.C., et al. (2024). Mixtures of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) alter sperm methylation and long-term reprogramming of offspring liver and fat transcriptome. *Environ. Int.* 186, 108577. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2024.108577>.
 52. Granum, B., Haug, L.S., Namork, E., Stølevik, S.B., Thomsen, C., Aaberge, I.S., van Loveren, H., Lovik, M., and Nygaard, U.C. (2013). Pre-natal exposure to perfluoroalkyl substances may be associated with altered vaccine antibody levels and immune-related health outcomes in early childhood. *J. Immunotoxicol.* 10, 373–379. <https://doi.org/10.3109/1547691x.2012.755580>.
 53. Timmermann, C.A.G., Jensen, K.J., Nielsen, F., Budtz-Jørgensen, E., van der Klis, F., Benn, C.S., Grandjean, P., and Fisker, A.B. (2020). Serum Perfluoroalkyl Substances, Vaccine Responses, and Morbidity in a Cohort of Guinea-Bissau Children. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 128, 87002. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp6517>.
 54. Vuong, A.M., Braun, J.M., Sjödin, A., Calafat, A.M., Yolton, K., Lanphear, B.P., and Chen, A. (2021). Exposure to endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs) and cardiometabolic indices during pregnancy: The HOME Study. *Environ. Int.* 156, 106747. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2021.106747>.
 55. Iipinen, A., Longnecker, M.P., Nygaard, U.C., London, S.J., Ferguson, K.K., Haug, L.S., and Granum, B. (2019). Maternal levels of perfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) during pregnancy and childhood allergy and asthma related outcomes and infections in the Norwegian Mother and Child (MoBa) cohort. *Environ. Int.* 124, 462–472. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2018.12.041>.
 56. Jackson-Browne, M.S., Eliot, M., Patti, M., Spanier, A.J., and Braun, J.M. (2020). PFAS (per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances) and asthma in young children: NHANES 2013–2014. *Int. J. Hyg. Environ. Health* 229, 113565. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2020.113565>.
 57. Standish, L.J., Sweet, E.S., Novack, J., Wenner, C.A., Bridge, C., Nelson, A., Martzen, M., and Torkelson, C. (2008). Breast cancer and the immune system. *J. Soc. Integr. Oncol.* 6, 158–168.
 58. Jiang, X., and Shapiro, D.J. (2014). The immune system and inflammation in breast cancer. *Mol. Cell. Endocrinol.* 382, 673–682. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mce.2013.06.003>.
 59. Bonefeld-Jørgensen, E.C., Boesen, S.A.H., Wielsøe, M., Henriksen, T.B., Bech, B.H., Halldórsson, Þ.I., and Long, M. (2023). Exposure to persistent organic pollutants in Danish pregnant women: Hormone levels and fetal growth indices. *Environ. Toxicol. Pharmacol.* 99, 104108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.etap.2023.104108>.
 60. Boesen, S.A.H., Long, M., Wielsøe, M., Mustieles, V., Fernandez, M.F., and Bonefeld-Jørgensen, E.C. (2020). Exposure to Perfluoroalkyl acids and foetal and maternal thyroid status: a review. *Environ. Health* 19, 107. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12940-020-00647-1>.
 61. Hjermslev, M.H., Long, M., Wielsøe, M., and Bonefeld-Jørgensen, E.C. (2020). Persistent organic pollutants in Greenlandic pregnant women and indices of foetal growth: The ACCEPT study. *Sci. Total Environ.* 698, 134118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.134118>.
 62. Bjerregaard-Olesen, C., Bach Cathrine, C., Long, M., Wielsøe, M., Bech Bodil, H., Henriksen Tine, B., Olsen, J., and Bonefeld-Jørgensen Eva, C. (2019). Associations of Fetal Growth Outcomes with Measures of the Combined Xenoestrogenic Activity of Maternal Serum Perfluorinated Alkyl Acids in Danish Pregnant Women. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 127, 17006. <https://doi.org/10.1289/EHP1884>.
 63. Bonefeld-Jørgensen, E.C., Long, M., Fredslund, S.O., Bossi, R., and Olsen, J. (2014). Breast cancer risk after exposure to perfluorinated compounds in Danish women: a case-control study nested in the Danish National Birth Cohort. *Cancer Causes Control* 25, 1439–1448. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10552-014-0446-7>.
 64. Torres, L., Redko, A., Limper, C., Imbiakha, B., Chang, S., and August, A. (2021). Effect of Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS) on immune cell development and function in mice. *Immunol. Lett.* 233, 31–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.imlet.2021.03.006>.
 65. Wang, L.Q., Liu, T., Yang, S., Sun, L., Zhao, Z.Y., Li, L.Y., She, Y.C., Zheng, Y.Y., Ye, X.Y., Bao, Q., et al. (2021). Perfluoroalkyl substance pollutants activate the innate immune system through the AIM2 inflammasome. *Nat. Commun.* 12, 2915. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-23201-0>.
 66. Palaniswamy, S., Nevala, L., Pesonen, P., Rautio, A., Järvelin, M.-R., Abass, K., and Charles, D. (2024). Environmental contaminants in Arctic human populations: Trends over 30 years. *Environ. Int.* 189, 108777. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2024.108777>.
 67. Wielsøe, M., Berthelsen, D., Mulvad, G., Isidor, S., Long, M., and Bonefeld-Jørgensen, E.C. (2021). Dietary habits among men and women in West Greenland: follow-up on the ACCEPT birth cohort. *BMC Public Health* 21, 1426. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-021-11359-7>.
 68. Knudsen, A.-K.S., Long, M., Pedersen, H.S., and Bonefeld-Jørgensen, E.C. (2015). Lifestyle, reproductive factors and food intake in Greenlandic pregnant women: The ACCEPT – sub-study. *Int. J. Circumpolar Health* 74, 29469. <https://doi.org/10.3402/ijch.v74.29469>.
 69. EFSA Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain (EFSA CONTAM Panel); Schrenk, D., Bignami, M., Bodin, L., Chipman, J.K., Del Mazo, J., Grasl-Kraupp, B., Hogstrand, C., Hoogenboom, L.R., and Leblanc, J.C. (2020). Risk to human health related to the presence of perfluoroalkyl substances in food. *EFSA J.* 18, e06223. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2020.6223>.
 70. European Food and Safety Authority (2020). Outcome of a public consultation on the draft risk assessment of perfluoroalkyl substances in food. *EFSA Support. Publ.* 17, 1931E. <https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2020.EN-1931>.
 71. Morris, A.D., Wilson, S.J., Fryer, R.J., Thomas, P.J., Hudelson, K., Andreasen, B., Blévin, P., Bustamante, P., Chastel, O., Christensen, G., et al. (2022). Temporal trends of mercury in Arctic biota: 10 more years of progress in Arctic monitoring. *Sci. Total Environ.* 839, 155803. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.155803>.

CRSUS, Volume 2

Supplemental information

Ubiquitous global use of persistent PFAS threatens

Arctic Indigenous peoples for decades to come

Christian Sonne, Kim Gustavson, Rossana Bossi, Jens Søndergaard, Jean-Pierre Desforges, Eva Cecilie Bonefeld-Jørgensen, and Rune Dietz

1 SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION FOR

2
3 **Ubiquitous global use of persistent PFAS threaten Arctic Indigenous people for decades to come**

4
5 Christian Sonne^{1,*,**}, Kim Gustavson¹, Rossana Bossi², Jens Søndergaard¹, Jean-Pierre Desforges³,
6 Eva Bonefeld-Jørgensen^{4,5}, Rune Dietz¹

7
8 ¹ Department of Ecoscience, Aarhus University, Arctic Research Centre; Frederiksborgvej 399, DK-
9 4000 Roskilde, Denmark.

10 ² Department of Environmental Science, Aarhus University; Frederiksborgvej 399, DK-4000
11 Roskilde, Denmark.

12 ³ Department of Environmental Studies and Science, 515 Portage Avenue, University of Winnipeg,
13 Winnipeg MB R3B 2E9, Canada.

14 ⁴ Department of Public Health, Centre for Arctic Health & Molecular Epidemiology, Aarhus
15 University; Build. 1260, Bartholin Allé 2, DK-8000 Aarhus C, Denmark.

16 ⁵ Greenland Centre for Health Research, University of Greenland, Nuuk, GRL-3905 Nuussuaq,
17 Greenland.

18 *Corresponding Author. Email: cs@ecos.au.dk (C. Sonne).

19 ** Lead Contact. Email: cs@ecos.au.dk (C. Sonne).

20 **Supplemental Notes**

21
22 **Note 1. Fieldwork and data collection**

23
24 1. Tissue collection.

25 Muscle and liver tissue was sampled from a total of 95 polar bears and 52 ringed seals sampled
26 during 2006-2020 during subsistence harvest in Ittoqqortoormiit (Scoresby Sound), East Greenland
27 (table S1, S2). In addition, a subset of 16 Ittoqqortoormiit inhabitants (7 subsistence hunters and 7
28 non-subsistence hunters) representing *ca.* 5% of the total population were randomly selected and
29 enrolled in September 2015. These filled out a culturally appropriate lifestyle questionnaire and a
30 specially designed food frequency questionnaire (FFQ) for Inuit with both questionnaires being
31 available in both Danish and Greenlandic. The FFQ included species, tissue (meat, organs,
32 intestines, eyes and brain), month and meals per week (one meal: <200g, two meals: 200-600g,
33 three meals: >600g). The FFQ further included imported food such as beef, pork, chicken/turkey,
34 non-Greenlandic fish, ready meals, vegetables, fruit and bread. This FFQ is frequently used in
35 Greenland for the study of traditional and western diets in relation to contaminant exposure and has
36 been optimized using experiences from previous FFQ cohorts in the Arctic ^{1,2}. Informed consent was
37 obtained from all participants prior to data collection. The study was approved by the Ethical
38 Committee for Scientific Investigations in Greenland (KVUG) and conducted in accordance with
39 the Helsinki Declaration. All samples obtained from polar bears were under the international IUCN
40 CITES regulations legally exported from Greenland (295/2000, 61/2001, 69/2001, 66/2003,
41 156/2004, 23/2005, 17/2006, 08GL0706599, 09GL0805839, 10GL0806166, 10GL0805167,
42 10GL0806333, 10GL0806334, 11GL1003311, 12GL1003376, 13GL1003418, 14GL1003515,
43 15GL1166847, 16GL1167015, 17GL1167116, 18GL1717224, 19GL1717365, 20GL1717427) to
44 Denmark (IM 0813-642/01, IM 0312-080/01, IM 1116-901/04, IM 1116-954/05, IM 0316-613/06,
45 IM 0811-266/06, IM 0711-993/08, IM 0630-137/09, IM 0611288/10, IM 0611-290/10, IM 1223-
46 856/10, IM 1223-855/10, IM 1214-596/11, IM 1199-728/12, IM 0826-378/13, IM 1202-211714, IM
47 1222-060/15, IM 1202-580/16, IM 0818-549/17, IM 0928-712/18, IM0816-496/19, DK2020-
48 0017113-01).

49
50 2. Weekly meat and liver consumption

51 Estimates for weekly consumption of polar bear meat (gram/week) and ringed seal meat and liver of
52 the 7 subsistence hunters and 7 non-subsistence hunters of Ittoqqortoormiit were based on data from
53 the FFQ (table S3).

54
55 **Note 2. PFAS concentrations and chemical analyses**

56
57 1. PFAS concentrations in ringed seals and polar bears

58 The concentration of PFAS in consumed polar bear meat and ringed seal meat and liver tissue in
59 Ittoqqortoormiit are shown in table S1, S2. A compilation of results from the interviews (table S3)
60 and concentrations of PFASs in harvest animals indicated that by far the largest intake of PFAS was
61 from the consumption of seals and polar bears. For example, narwhal, walrus, harp seal, hooded seal
62 and bearded seals can be neglected as hardly any muscle is consumed from these species. In addition,
63 seabirds and muskoxen were also important food items but insignificant in terms of PFAS exposure
64 due to their low PFAS tissue concentrations.

65
66 2. PFAS chemical analyses in muscle and liver tissue

67 PFAS were analysed at the Department of Environmental Science, Aarhus University, Roskilde,
68 Denmark. The PFASs quantified included perfluorobutanesulfonic acid (PFBS),

69 perfluorohexanesulfonic acid (PFHxS), perfluoroheptanesulfonic acid (PFHpS),
70 perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS), perfluorodecanesulfonic acid (PFDS), perfluoro-1-
71 octanesulfonamide (FOSA), perfluorohexanoic acid (PFHxA), perfluoroheptanoic acid (PFHpA),
72 perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA), perfluorononanoic acid (PFNA), perfluorodecanoic acid (PFDA),
73 perfluoroundecanoic acid (PFUnA), perfluorododecanoic acid (PFDoA), perfluorotridecanoic acid
74 (PFTrA), and perfluorotetradecanoic acid (PFTeA). Approximately 5 g of muscle or liver tissue was
75 homogenised and 1g aliquot was weighted in a polypropylene tube and spiked with 10 ng ¹³C-labelled
76 PFAS. Native and labelled compounds were bought as mixtures from Wellington Laboratories
77 (Guelph, ON, Canada). Tissues were extracted with 5 mL of acetonitrile twice for 30 min in an
78 ultrasonic bath at 30 °C. The combined extract was reduced to 2 mL under a stream of nitrogen and
79 50 µL of acetic acid were added. For clean-up, Supelclean ENVI-Carb[®] cartridges (100 mg, 1 mL,
80 100-400 mesh, Supelco, USA) were used. The cartridges were conditioned with 2 mL of acetonitrile
81 followed by 1 mL of 20% acetic acid in acetonitrile. Afterwards, the sample extract was added to the
82 cartridge with three times 1 mL of methanol and directly collected into another vial. The extracts were
83 dried under a gentle nitrogen stream and reconstituted in 1 mL of methanol:ammonium acetate (2
84 mM; 50:50 v:v). Instrumental analysis was performed by liquid chromatography-tandem mass
85 spectrometry (LC-MS-MS) with electrospray ionization (ESI) in negative mode using an Agilent
86 1290 Infinity Series HPLC coupled to a 6495 triple quadrupole mass spectrometer (Agilent). The ions
87 monitored for each compound can be found in Sonne et al. (2019). Each batch of samples was
88 analysed with a procedural blank and two control samples (certified reference material). Recoveries
89 ranged from 75-129 % and the relative standard deviation (RSD) for samples run in duplicate ranged
90 from 5-24 % (Sonne et al. 2019). The RSDs for PFTeA and PFTrA were higher (44%-47%) because
91 the corresponding mass-labelled chemical standards were not available. Method detection limits were
92 calculated as three times the standard deviation of procedural blanks.

93

94 **References**

- 95 1. Wielsøe, M., Berthelsen, D., Mulvad, G., Isidor, S., Long, M., Bonefeld-Jørgensen, E.C. (2021).
96 Dietary habits among men and women in West Greenland: follow-up on the ACCEPT birth cohort.
97 BMC Public Health 21, 1426. doi.org/10.1186/s12889-021-11359-7.
- 98 2. Knudsen A.,K.,S., Long, M., Pedersen, H.S., Bonefeld-Jørgensen, E.C. (2015). Lifestyle,
99 reproductive factors and food intake in Greenlandic pregnant women: The ACCEPT – sub-study.
100 International Journal of Circumpolar Health 74, 29469. doi.org/10.3402/ijch.v74.29469.
- 101 3. Sonne, C., Vorkamp, K., Galatius, A, et al. (2019). Human exposure to PFOS and mercury
102 through meat from baltic harbour seals (*Phoca vitulina*). Environmental Research 175, 376-83.
103 doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2019.05.026.

104 **Supplemental Tables**

105

106

107 **Table S1. Weekly consumption of seal and polar bear tissues**

108 Ringed seal liver and ringed seal and polar bear muscle (gram/week) consumed by residents (8
 109 subsistence hunters and 8 non-subsistence hunters) in Ittoqqortoormiit, East Greenland. Data was
 110 gathered from food frequency questionnaires. The average, standard deviation (SD) and median
 111 of all samples is summarized in the bottom rows.

Weekly muscle, liver and total consumption (g/wk)				
Participant ID	Ringed seal muscle	Ringed seal liver	Polar bear muscle	Sum all
1	42	0	0	42
2	100	0	42	142
3	100	0	100	200
4	200	133	100	433
5	100	100	42	242
6	133	133	83	349
7	200	133	42	375
8	83	0	17	100
9	200	200	100	500
10	200	267	42	509
11	42	0	100	142
12	200	200	83	483
13	200	200	42	442
14	167	83	42	292
15	140	104	60	304
16	62	89	34	185
<i>Average</i>	<i>136</i>	<i>103</i>	<i>58</i>	<i>296</i>
<i>SD</i>	<i>59</i>	<i>83</i>	<i>31</i>	<i>147</i>
<i>Median</i>	<i>136.5</i>	<i>102</i>	<i>42</i>	<i>298</i>

112

113 **Table S2. Concentration of PFAS in seal tissues**

114 Σ_4 PFAS in muscle and liver tissue of ringed seals in East Greenland (ng/g wet weight) sampled
 115 spring 2006-2020. Average, standard deviation (SD) and median of all samples are summarized
 116 below. M: male. F: female.

Seal-ID	Year	Age	Sex	Subseries	PFHxSmuscle	PFOSmuscle	PFOamuscle	PFNAmuscle	Σ_4 muscle	PFHxSliver	PFOSliver	PFOAliver	PFNAliver	Σ_4 liver
34901	2006	21	m	adult	0.1	4.0	0.3	0.2	4.6	0.8	180.0	7.0	14.7	202.5
34910	2006	2	m	subadult	0.1	2.2	0.1	0.1	2.6	0.9	59.8	0.0	2.3	63.0
34912	2006	1	m	subadult	0.2	1.9	0.1	0.1	2.3	0.0	481.0	0.0	1.6	482.6
34914	2006	7	m	adult	1.0	3.0	0.2	2.4	6.6	0.0	251.0	2.9	5.6	259.5
34917	2006	0	m	subadult	1.2	2.2	0.1	1.9	5.4	0.8	246.0	2.4	2.7	251.9
38001	2008	1	f	subadult	0.1	1.5	0.0	0.2	1.8	0.0	235.0	2.8	9.0	246.8
38005	2008	6	m	adult	0.2	3.5	0.2	0.3	4.0	0.0	274.0	2.6	7.0	283.7
38010	2008	1	m	subadult	0.3	3.0	0.1	0.6	4.0	0.0	337.0	0.0	4.9	341.9
38014	2008	3	m	subadult	1.2	3.0	0.1	1.1	5.3	0.0	232.0	0.0	8.3	240.3
38018	2008	2	m	subadult	1.2	5.2	0.2	2.1	8.7	0.0	385.0	0.0	11.7	396.7
38104	2010	4	f	subadult	1.4	2.2	0.1	2.0	5.7	0.0	100.4	0.0	17.7	118.1
38107	2010	18	m	adult	1.3	12.9	0.3	2.2	16.6	0.0	97.2	0.0	6.7	103.9
38112	2010	3	f	subadult	1.0	9.6	0.2	1.7	12.6	0.0	158.0	0.0	0.0	158.0
38116	2010	4	f	subadult	0.7	7.5	0.1	1.1	9.5	0.0	139.0	0.0	19.0	158.0
38120	2010	3	m	subadult	1.2	5.5	0.1	1.6	8.5	0.0	134.0	0.0	5.7	139.7
43401	2018	1	f	subadult	1.9	1.5	0.1	1.6	5.0	0.9	27.7	0.1	7.5	36.2
43402	2018	1	m	subadult	1.6	3.6	0.2	1.9	7.3	0.9	27.5	0.3	10.9	39.6
43403	2018	1	m	subadult	1.5	4.4	0.2	2.5	8.6	0.9	26.2	0.1	9.0	36.2
43404	2018	1	f	subadult	1.9	2.2	0.1	2.5	6.7	0.9	23.4	0.0	6.4	30.7
43407	2018	10	f	adult	3.6	2.5	0.2	6.4	12.6	0.8	26.3	0.1	7.0	34.1
43409	2018	2	f	subadult	1.6	2.2	0.1	3.2	7.0	1.0	35.8	0.2	8.7	45.7
43410	2018	1	f	subadult	1.8	3.0	0.1	2.9	7.8	1.0	23.4	0.2	8.8	33.3
43411	2018	17	m	adult	1.4	1.7	0.1	2.4	5.5	1.2	35.5	0.9	13.8	51.4
43412	2018	1	f	subadult	0.8	2.3	0.1	1.8	4.9	1.0	21.2	0.1	6.0	28.4
43414	2018	5	m	adult	1.9	2.7	0.1	2.4	7.1	1.0	30.0	0.1	6.8	37.9
43415	2018	5	m	adult	1.2	2.3	0.1	1.5	5.1	1.2	33.8	0.1	8.5	43.6
43416	2018	7	f	adult	1.7	1.9	0.1	2.9	6.5	1.1	23.8	0.0	5.2	30.1
43417	2018	1	f	subadult	1.6	2.3	0.1	4.6	8.6	1.0	18.0	0.0	4.0	22.9
43418	2018	8	m	adult	2.7	2.1	0.1	6.7	11.5	1.8	46.5	0.8	16.1	65.1
43421	2018	14	m	adult	1.4	1.7	0.1	2.4	5.7	1.4	51.2	0.9	14.1	67.6
43422	2018	6	m	adult	0.0	2.1	0.1	0.2	2.4	1.1	27.0	0.1	6.5	34.6
43423	2018	14	f	adult	0.0	1.9	0.1	0.3	2.3	1.0	28.7	0.1	6.7	36.5
46702	2012	0	m	subadult	0.1	4.8	0.4	0.3	5.5	0.8	77.5	0.8	10.1	89.2
46710	2012	1	m	subadult	0.2	6.1	0.3	0.6	7.1	0.8	88.3	0.5	12.9	102.5
46713	2012	4	f	subadult	0.2	3.4	0.2	0.5	4.3	0.7	61.1	0.1	6.3	68.2
46716	2012	1	f	subadult	0.5	3.1	0.3	1.1	5.1	0.7	57.4	0.2	11.2	69.4
46725	2012	7	m	adult	1.1	2.5	0.2	1.7	5.6	0.8	64.9	2.5	13.2	81.4
50301	2014	9	m	adult	0.4	0.6	0.1	0.8	2.0	0.0	22.4	1.7	10.8	35.0
50304	2014	0	f	subadult	0.3	2.4	0.1	0.5	3.3	0.7	35.5	0.3	4.3	40.7
50307	2014	10	m	adult	0.2	1.6	0.2	0.2	2.3	0.0	54.1	1.4	11.2	66.7
50313	2014	10	m	adult	1.0	3.5	0.2	1.6	6.3	0.0	53.4	1.4	13.9	68.6
50316	2014	2	m	subadult	2.8	3.0	0.3	3.8	9.9	0.9	56.9	0.7	13.4	71.9
54744	2016	5	m	adult	0.2	3.1	0.2	0.4	3.8	0.6	59.1	0.7	11.4	71.7
54747	2016	9	m	adult	0.2	1.9	0.2	0.6	2.8	0.8	74.2	1.2	18.8	94.9
54751	2016	18	m	adult	0.1	6.2	0.3	0.5	7.1	0.0	112.0	2.2	26.5	140.7
54760	2016	1	m	subadult	0.1	3.6	0.3	0.4	4.4	0.0	60.3	0.3	9.2	69.8
54764	2016	0	f	subadult	0.1	1.9	0.1	0.3	2.4	0.0	28.5	0.2	4.0	32.7
63653	2020	4	m	subadult	0.1	2.0	0.2	0.4	2.6	0.0	44.5	0.0	8.8	53.3
63656	2020	5	f	adult	0.2	3.0	0.2	0.5	3.9	0.8	101.4	0.3	17.1	119.6
63660	2020	2	m	subadult	0.2	3.1	0.2	0.5	3.9	0.7	53.1	0.0	14.2	68.0
63663	2020	6	m	adult	0.2	3.3	0.2	0.7	4.3	1.3	53.8	0.7	15.2	71.0
63667	2020	5	m	adult	0.1	2.1	0.1	0.3	2.6	0.6	79.0	0.0	16.5	96.1
<i>Average</i>					0.9	3.2	0.2	1.5	5.8	0.6	97.2	0.7	9.8	108.3
<i>SD</i>					0.8	2.1	0.1	1.5	3.1	0.5	101.9	1.2	5.2	101.3
<i>Median</i>					0.8	2.6	0.1	1.1	5.4	0.8	57.1	0.2	8.9	69.0

118 **Table S3. Concentration of PFAS in polar bear tissues**

119 Σ_4 PFAS in muscle and liver tissue of polar bears in East Greenland (ng/g wet weight) sampled
 120 spring 2006-2020. Average, standard deviation (SD) and median of all samples are summarized
 121 below. M: male. F: female.

Bear-ID	Year	Age	Sex	Subseries	PFHxSmuscle	PFOSmuscle	PFOamuscle	PFNAmuscle	Σ_4 muscle	PFHxSliver	PFOSliver	PFOAliver	PFNAliver	Σ_4 liver
33921	2006	6	M	adult	1.6	20.3	0.7	2.1	24.7	19.4	2712.0	9.8	204.0	2945.2
33923	2007	4	F	subadult	1.3	14.3	0.7	1.3	17.6	20.3	4180.7	63.9	604.2	4869.0
33931	2006	8	M	adult	1.8	30.5	0.3	1.6	34.2	15.0	3776.0	9.6	286.0	4086.6
33933	2007	13	M	adult	2.2	25.9	0.5	1.9	30.5	23.3	3631.3	12.2	334.6	4001.4
33943	2007	5	M	subadult	3.6	29.1	0.8	3.7	37.1	16.2	2250.8	7.9	268.4	2543.3
33944	2006	12	F	adult	2.0	29.6	0.4	1.9	33.8	7.2	3456.0	13.6	286.0	3762.8
33948	2006	4	M	subadult	1.8	14.5	0.5	1.1	17.9	14.3	3056.0	17.2	214.0	3301.5
33952	2006	8	F	adult	1.1	11.5	0.2	0.7	13.5	16.0	3340.0	14.0	212.0	3582.0
33954	2007	9	M	adult	0.1	21.3	0.9	0.4	22.7	10.1	2823.0	28.4	531.8	3393.3
33958	2007	6	F	adult	0.4	15.5	1.1	0.1	17.1	11.4	2435.5	19.7	214.5	2681.1
35164	2014	2	F	subadult	1.2	9.3	0.7	1.6	12.7	5.2	634.5	7.5	147.0	794.2
35166	2014	6	M	adult	1.4	13.7	0.8	2.4	18.2	5.1	415.5	9.4	113.5	543.6
35169	2014	8	M	adult	2.7	27.7	0.9	4.1	35.4	6.1	556.0	9.3	194.0	765.4
35171	2014	3	F	subadult	0.1	7.4	0.7	0.1	8.3	8.0	619.0	17.8	178.5	823.3
35172	2014	5	M	subadult	0.2	14.1	0.8	0.4	15.6	4.7	343.0	9.0	118.0	474.7
39465	2010	8	M	adult	0.1	20.1	0.9	0.2	21.2	11.4	1560.0	11.0	125.5	1707.9
39469	2010	7	M	adult	0.3	16.0	0.4	1.0	17.7	10.5	1275.0	12.1	165.5	1463.1
39471	2010	8	M	adult	0.4	12.3	0.6	0.7	14.0	0.0	154.0	0.0	6.3	160.3
39473	2010	3	M	subadult	0.5	5.4	0.5	0.6	7.0	9.2	1215.0	11.2	79.6	1315.0
39486	2010	2	M	subadult	0.3	11.3	0.7	0.5	12.8	9.3	648.0	16.0	154.0	827.3
39710	2008	5	F	adult	1.6	14.2	1.4	2.1	19.2	28.3	1890.0	24.5	197.5	2140.3
39716	2008	5	M	adult	1.7	16.1	0.8	1.8	20.5	27.9	1405.0	9.0	174.0	1615.8
39718	2008	10	M	adult	2.0	23.0	0.7	1.9	27.5	32.2	2680.0	10.8	230.0	2953.0
39723	2008	19	M	adult	2.2	32.6	0.9	2.9	38.7	27.8	1876.0	4.9	239.0	2147.7
39729	2008	19	M	adult	1.5	17.7	0.6	2.1	21.9	12.3	1620.0	10.3	305.0	1947.6
39859	2009	7	F	adult	0.6	4.8	0.6	0.7	6.7	20.6	3308.9	60.9	576.0	3966.4
39861	2009	16	M	adult	5.0	49.3	0.3	6.5	61.1	15.4	2325.8	5.7	214.3	2561.1
39865	2009	13	M	adult	5.5	62.0	1.1	5.8	74.4	23.5	4147.4	27.0	626.9	4824.8
39870	2009	13	M	adult	2.5	19.9	1.0	2.2	25.6	23.8	2534.1	11.1	316.0	2885.0
39871	2009	8	M	adult	2.0	17.3	0.5	2.6	22.3	21.2	3147.2	32.4	526.8	3727.5
43102	2011	4	M	subadult	0.3	14.4	0.4	0.6	15.8	8.1	654.0	4.8	115.0	781.8
43103	2011	2	F	subadult	0.3	9.7	0.9	0.8	11.8	4.7	916.5	10.1	172.0	1103.3
43105	2011	3	F	subadult	0.2	15.2	0.7	0.3	16.3	4.0	1495.0	2.3	160.0	1661.3
43107	2011	1	F	subadult	0.2	14.6	0.6	0.4	15.9	4.5	841.5	4.1	247.5	1097.6
43109	2011	11	M	adult	0.3	38.3	1.0	0.3	39.9	2.2	1360.0	3.1	254.5	1619.8
46751	2012	2	M	subadult	0.8	22.0	0.8	0.8	24.3	5.5	509.5	7.2	111.5	633.7
46753	2012	6	M	adult	2.1	16.1	0.7	5.4	24.3	7.2	481.0	6.9	106.2	601.2
46755	2012	5	F	adult	1.2	13.0	1.0	2.5	17.8	4.9	605.5	8.9	150.0	769.2
46758	2012	5	M	subadult	0.9	10.0	0.6	1.5	13.0	3.9	583.0	10.7	148.5	746.1
46760	2012	2	M	subadult	1.6	14.5	0.8	2.0	18.8	11.3	1010.0	9.3	199.5	1230.0
48702	2013	2	F	subadult	2.1	9.1	0.6	3.5	15.3	6.2	493.0	12.7	117.0	628.9
48704	2013	2	M	subadult	1.7	16.1	0.7	4.0	22.4	3.3	455.0	4.1	94.4	556.8
48706	2013	14	M	adult	1.9	29.3	0.7	3.6	35.5	5.8	1250.0	5.9	215.0	1476.7
48708	2013	8	M	adult	0.2	42.3	1.1	0.4	44.0	5.8	901.0	6.1	168.0	1080.9
48710	2013	3	M	subadult	0.2	14.8	0.7	0.3	15.9	4.6	691.0	7.3	110.0	812.8
50414	2015	4	M	subadult	2.0	6.6	0.6	2.1	11.3	4.2	446.0	6.6	114.5	571.4
50416	2015	21	M	adult	2.0	13.5	0.5	2.3	18.3	6.1	545.0	7.3	148.0	706.3
50418	2015	1	M	subadult	1.1	6.3	0.7	2.5	10.5	3.8	431.5	11.0	96.0	542.3
50420	2015	12	F	adult	0.1	28.6	0.7	0.3	29.7	7.9	902.8	3.2	149.8	1063.7
50422	2015	6	M	adult	0.3	14.2	0.9	1.0	16.3	5.2	508.5	6.2	127.0	646.9
53421	2016	16	M	adult	0.4	8.4	0.6	1.4	10.7	8.0	1160.0	11.6	211.0	1390.6
53424	2016	12	M	adult	0.2	9.4	0.5	0.6	10.7	11.8	1100.0	17.0	359.8	1488.5
53426	2016	5	M	subadult	0.1	21.4	1.3	0.6	23.3	8.8	1415.0	26.6	326.0	1776.3
53428	2016	3	M	subadult	0.1	18.5	1.5	0.4	20.4	6.6	620.0	15.3	175.5	817.4
53429	2016	3	F	subadult	0.2	21.1	0.5	0.7	22.5	9.4	1360.0	7.5	290.0	1666.9
57202	2017	5	M	subadult	0.1	9.7	0.5	0.3	10.7	7.5	977.3	12.9	269.3	1266.9
57204	2017	3	M	subadult	0.2	19.2	1.1	0.4	20.9	6.4	937.5	13.0	219.0	1175.9
57206	2017	5	M	subadult	0.1	13.6	0.9	0.3	14.7	11.5	1030.0	17.1	258.0	1316.6
57209	2017	6	M	adult	0.1	15.6	0.8	0.4	16.9	14.0	1520.0	19.7	369.0	1922.8
57213	2017	9	M	adult	0.2	12.8	0.8	0.3	14.1	8.4	1480.0	23.7	395.5	1907.6
59101	2018	6	M	adult	1.3	11.6	0.4	2.4	15.7	2.5	294.0	3.9	95.2	395.7
59102	2018	16	M	adult	1.3	16.8	0.4	3.7	22.2	4.4	1554.0	11.0	411.7	1981.1
59103	2018	2	F	subadult	0.9	6.6	0.4	1.7	9.5	10.5	968.0	17.6	263.7	1259.7
59104	2018	2	F	subadult	0.8	6.8	0.5	1.7	9.7	5.0	796.0	11.1	167.7	979.9

59105	2018	10	M	adult	1.8	17.0	0.5	3.5	22.7	12.2	1302.0	9.0	261.7	1584.9
59106	2018	8	M	adult	0.9	9.3	0.4	2.0	12.5	8.2	807.0	6.6	181.1	1002.9
59107	2018	8	M	adult	2.9	15.1	1.0	4.3	23.3	15.4	986.0	11.9	239.7	1253.0
59108	2018	12	M	adult	0.8	6.0	0.4	1.6	8.7	12.7	1227.0	19.0	354.7	1613.3
59109	2018	6	F	adult	0.9	7.1	0.6	1.7	10.3	15.0	645.0	11.6	159.0	830.6
59110	2018	7	M	adult	1.1	9.9	0.5	1.8	13.3	11.4	1126.0	14.3	230.7	1382.4
59111	2018	7	F	adult	1.5	8.6	0.2	1.6	11.9	10.9	521.0	2.9	130.6	665.4
59112	2018	8	F	adult	2.8	16.4	0.6	4.0	23.7	35.1	1395.0	19.2	510.7	1960.0
59113	2018	6		adult	1.8	19.0	0.6	3.2	24.4	22.9	1481.0	8.1	334.7	1846.7
59114	2018	6	M	adult	1.4	11.6	0.6	3.2	16.7	6.3	446.0	4.9	131.5	588.7
59115	2018	10	F	adult	2.0	15.3	0.4	5.6	23.3	14.6	1480.5	4.5	339.7	1839.2
61851	2019	12	M	adult	2.1	16.1	0.6	3.8	22.6	16.9	2040.0	24.5	606.0	2687.4
61852	2019	4	M	subadult	0.8	6.5	0.4	1.8	9.5	7.5	529.0	9.9	206.4	752.8
61853	2019	4	F	subadult	1.2	6.6	0.1	1.5	9.4	10.4	791.0	6.2	254.0	1061.6
61854	2019	16	M	adult	1.5	18.8	0.8	4.8	25.8	10.0	1552.0	14.7	416.0	1992.7
61855	2019	2	M	subadult	1.1	7.4	0.4	1.6	10.5	10.8	907.0	20.4	270.0	1208.2
61856	2019	2	M	subadult	1.0	7.6	0.5	2.0	11.1	5.7	716.0	18.0	223.0	962.8
61857	2019	4	F	subadult	0.8	9.0	0.7	2.5	13.1	7.3	1338.0	28.8	352.7	1726.8
61858	2019	3	M	subadult	0.7	5.5	0.4	1.5	7.9	2.2	427.0	10.2	161.6	601.0
61859	2019	9	M	adult	1.7	12.4	0.5	2.9	17.6	17.5	1561.0	26.3	581.0	2185.8
61860	2019	3	F	subadult	1.4	8.6	0.6	2.8	13.3	13.0	458.0	9.7	110.4	591.2
61861	2019	9	M	adult	1.1	10.4	0.5	3.0	14.9	12.6	1689.0	15.5	446.0	2163.1
61862	2019	4	M	subadult	1.1	8.8	0.5	2.3	12.5	7.6	876.0	12.1	262.0	1157.7
61863	2019	5	M	subadult	0.8	8.7	0.5	2.8	12.8	5.4	709.0	6.2	165.8	886.4
61864	2019	6	M	adult	0.8	6.5	0.3	2.1	9.7	4.4	826.5	6.5	223.5	1060.9
61865	2019	10	F	adult	1.3	14.3	0.3	3.8	19.7	10.2	1947.0	13.0	578.0	2548.2
61881	2020	5.5	M	adult	1.3	8.4	1.5	2.6	13.7	12.8	1636.0	30.1	449.7	2128.5
61883	2020	7.5	M	adult	1.1	7.7	0.7	1.4	10.8	14.8	1402.5	26.9	391.2	1835.4
61886	2020	7.5	M	adult	1.4	11.3	0.9	2.1	15.7	12.7	1637.6	29.1	436.9	2116.2
61890	2020	17	M	adult	0.9	11.7	0.4	1.4	14.4	11.7	2818.0	11.3	508.4	3349.4
61893	2020	3	F	subadult	1.1	12.8	0.8	3.2	18.0	11.7	1628.9	17.9	457.5	2115.9
<i>Average</i>					<i>1.2</i>	<i>15.6</i>	<i>0.7</i>	<i>2.0</i>	<i>19.4</i>	<i>11.0</i>	<i>1381.2</i>	<i>13.6</i>	<i>259.3</i>	<i>1665.1</i>
<i>SD</i>					<i>1.0</i>	<i>9.5</i>	<i>0.3</i>	<i>1.4</i>	<i>10.7</i>	<i>7.0</i>	<i>942.1</i>	<i>10.2</i>	<i>141.9</i>	<i>1048.8</i>
<i>Median</i>					<i>1.1</i>	<i>14.2</i>	<i>0.6</i>	<i>1.8</i>	<i>16.9</i>	<i>10.0</i>	<i>1160.0</i>	<i>11.0</i>	<i>219.0</i>	<i>1390.6</i>

123 **Table S4. Temporal trends for PFAS**

124 Statistics for Σ_4 PFAS (PFOS, PFOA, PFNA, PFHxS) in polar bear and ringed seal from Ittoqqortoormiit (Scoresby Sound), East

125 Greenland, during 2006-2020 using the HARSAT model.

Species	Tissue	PFAS	N	Number of years	P (non-linear)	P (log-linear)	Annual change (%)	Fitted mean-concentration last year (ng/g w.w.)
Polar bear	Liver	PFHXS	95	15	<0.001	0.230	-3.8	12.7
Polar bear	Liver	PFNA	95	15	0.002	0.517	1.6	411.3
Polar bear	Liver	PFOA	95	15	0.005	0.733	0.5	18.1
Polar bear	Liver	PFOS	95	15	<0.001	0.048	-7.0	1499.9
Polar bear	Liver	Σ_4 PFAS	95	15	<0.001	0.093	-5.7	1952.1
Polar bear	Muscle	PFHXS	95	15	n.s.	0.337	-4.8	0.5
Polar bear	Muscle	PFNA	95	15	n.s.	0.617	2.0	1.4
Polar bear	Muscle	PFOA	95	15	n.s.	0.754	-0.5	0.6
Polar bear	Muscle	PFOS	95	15	n.s.	<0.001	-5.6	9.7
Polar bear	Muscle	Σ_4 PFAS	95	15	n.s.	<0.001	-4.2	13.5
Ringed seal	Liver	PFHXS	52	8	n.s.	0.176	2.6	0.8
Ringed seal	Liver	PFNA	52	8	n.s.	0.016	5.4	11.9
Ringed seal	Liver	PFOA	52	8	n.s.	0.013	-18.7	0.1
Ringed seal	Liver	PFOS	52	8	n.s.	0.002	-13.3	32.5
Ringed seal	Liver	Σ_4 PFAS	52	8	n.s.	0.003	-11.7	42.7
Ringed seal	Muscle	PFHXS	52	8	n.s.	0.659	-2.7	0.3
Ringed seal	Muscle	PFNA	52	8	n.s.	0.574	2.8	0.9
Ringed seal	Muscle	PFOA	52	8	n.s.	0.730	1.0	0.2
Ringed seal	Muscle	PFOS	52	8	n.s.	0.314	-2.6	2.5
Ringed seal	Muscle	Σ_4 PFAS	52	8	n.s.	0.659	-1.1	4.5

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130 **Figure S1. Temporal trends of PFOS in Ittoqortoormiit, East Greenland 2006-2020**

131 Figure S1a shows annual medians and 95% confidence bands for polar bear liver PFOS; Figure
 132 S1b shows annual medians and 95% confidence bands for polar bear muscle PFOS; Figure S1c
 133 shows annual medians and 95% confidence bands for ringed seal liver PFOS; Figure S1d shows
 134 annual medians and 95% confidence bands for ringed seal muscle PFAS.

135 **Figure S2. Temporal trends of PFOA in Ittoqqortoormiit, East Greenland 2006-2020**
 136 Figure S2a shows annual medians and 95% confidence bands for PFOA in polar bear liver; Figure
 137 S2b shows annual medians and 95% confidence bands for PFOA in polar bear muscle; Figure S2c
 138 shows annual medians and 95% confidence bands for PFOA in ringed seal liver; Figure S2d shows
 139 annual medians and 95% confidence bands for PFOA in ringed seal muscle.
 140

141 **Figure S3. Temporal trends of PFNA in Ittoqqortoormiit, East Greenland 2006-2020**
 142 Figure S3a shows annual medians and 95% confidence bands for PFNA in polar bear liver; Figure
 143 S3b shows annual medians and 95% confidence bands for PFNA in polar bear muscle; Figure S3c
 144 shows annual medians and 95% confidence bands for PFNA in ringed seal liver; Figure S3d shows
 145 annual medians and 95% confidence bands for PFNA in ringed seal muscle.
 146

147 **Figure S3. Temporal trends of PFHxS in Ittoqqortoormiit, East Greenland 2006-2020**
 148
 149 Figure S4a shows annual medians and 95% confidence bands for PFHxS in polar bear liver; Figure
 150 S4b shows annual medians and 95% confidence bands for PFHxS in polar bear muscle; Figure
 151 S4c shows annual medians and 95% confidence bands for PFHxS in ringed seal liver; Figure S4d
 152 shows annual medians and 95% confidence bands for PFHxS in ringed seal muscle.